

ISic3492

I.Sicily inscription 3492

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8711

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ὑάκινθε χρηστὲ καὶ
2. ἄμεμπτε χαῖρε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645113

EDR 140744

EDCS 41300106

PHI 175747

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 57.0871

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 142

Vinci, M. 2007. Un nuovo epitaffio in greco della Sicilia di età alto-imperiale e il formulario con gli epiteti XPHSTOS KAI AMEMPTOS. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik*. 162: 188-192. At 189-190

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3492. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358608>